

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF NLP TECHNOLOGIES FOR DATA EXTRACTION FROM TEXT MESSAGES IN MARITIME LOGISTICS

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Abstract

The article examines modern methods of integrating Natural Language Processing (NLP) technologies into the logistics sector: text preprocessing, named entity recognition, sentiment analysis, classification and clustering, and deep learning models. Their role in enhancing efficiency and accuracy of data extraction from textual messages is highlighted. Various NLP techniques and tools, their application in maritime logistics, as well as the challenges and limitations in their implementation are analyzed.

Keywords: neural networks, Natural Language Processing, maritime logistics, data extraction, textual messages, automation, customer satisfaction.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) represents a promising avenue for application across various industries, including logistics. As logistics operations increasingly rely on diverse and voluminous textual data – from shipment tracking information and customer inquiries to inventory records and route planning – there is a growing need for sophisticated tools capable of processing and extracting valuable insights from this unstructured data. NLP, a subfield of AI focused on the interaction between computers and human language, offers powerful solutions for automating and optimizing these processes. By leveraging NLP, logistics companies can significantly improve their operational workflows, reduce manual errors, and enhance customer satisfaction.

The primary aim of this study is to provide a detailed analysis of the application of NLP technologies for data extraction from text messages in the logistics industry. This involves examining the various NLP techniques and tools employed in logistics, highlighting successful case studies, and identifying the challenges and limitations faced in the practical implementation of these technologies.

Main part

The market for NLP is expanding rapidly, driven by the increasing demand for advanced data processing capabilities across various industries, including logistics. According to Statista, the market size for NLP is expected to reach 156,8 billion dollars by 2030 (figure 1).

Figure 1. Projected market size for NLP, billion dollars [7]

This growth is indicative of the widespread adoption of NLP technologies and their significant potential to transform industries by enabling more intelligent and efficient data extraction and analysis.

Technologies and methods

The application of NLP technology in maritime shipping is a promising direction that may transform methods of managing and utilizing textual data. This will enable the maritime industry to more efficiently process and extract meaningful information from vast amounts of unstructured text data, such as emails, reports, customer inquiries, and regulatory documents.

For companies, this will lead to increased operational efficiency and improved decision-making processes.

Text pre-processing is a step in NLP that involves cleaning and preparing raw text data for further analysis [4]. This process ensures that the text is in a suitable format for subsequent NLP tasks and includes several techniques:

- **Tokenization:** this involves splitting the text into individual units such as words or phrases. In maritime shipping, tokenization helps in breaking down lengthy documents like shipping manifests and bills of lading into manageable pieces.

- **Lemmatization and stemming:** These methods reduce words to their base or root forms. Lemmatization considers the context and converts words to their dictionary form (e.g., «running» to «run»). Stemming is the process of reducing a word to its base or root form by removing suffixes, often to normalize words for text processing; for example, the words «running», «runner» and «ran» are reduced to the root «run». This is crucial for ensuring consistency in text data and improving the accuracy of analysis.

- **Part-of-Speech Tagging:** This technique identifies the grammatical structure of the text by tagging each word with its respective part of speech (e.g., noun, verb, adjective). It is particularly useful in understanding the syntactic context of shipping documents and communications.

Text pre-processing is a step in NLP that offers significant advantages for maritime logistics by enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of data extraction

from unstructured text, such as emails, reports, and shipping manifests. The benefits include improved data consistency and reduced manual effort in handling vast amounts of textual information. Challenges include potential integration issues with existing systems, which may require significant resources and expertise to resolve effectively.

Named Entity Recognition (NER) is a NLP technique that focuses on identifying and classifying key entities within text into predefined categories such as names of persons, organizations, locations, dates, and more. In the context of maritime shipping, NER can be utilized to automate the extraction and categorization of critical information from unstructured text sources like emails, reports, and regulatory documents. This enhances data accuracy and retrieval, ultimately improving operational efficiency (table 1).

Table 1.

Applications of NER in maritime shipping [3]

Use Case	Description	Benefits
Ship names and identification	NER can identify and classify ship names from emails and customer service inquiries, ensuring up-to-date and accurate records.	Reduced manual effort, accurate record-keeping, efficient logistics operations.
Port locations	NER can extract mentions of port locations from shipment documents and communications.	Efficient route planning, reduced transit times and costs.
Cargo categorization	NER can categorize different types of cargo from bills of lading and shipment details.	Accurate inventory management, reduced manual errors, compliance with regulatory documentation.
Dates and schedules	NER can automatically extract shipment and delivery dates from various documents.	Precise schedules, improved reliability of deliveries, reduced downtime.
Regulatory compliance	NER can identify and categorize compliance-related information from international shipping regulations	Streamlined compliance checks, reduced legal risks, efficient documentation

Implementing NER in maritime logistics can be a challenging task due to the complexity and variability of maritime-related text data, such as different formats and terminologies used in shipping documents. Integrating NER systems with existing logistics infrastructure requires substantial technical expertise and resources to ensure seamless operation and accuracy. Despite these challenges, the benefits of NER in maritime shipping are substantial, making it an invaluable tool in the industry's digital transformation efforts.

Sentiment analysis, also known as opinion mining, is a powerful NLP technique that can be employed to extract and interpret the emotional tone of textual data in maritime logistics (MTL). It can be used to monitor and evaluate customer satisfaction by analyzing feedback from various communication channels [1]. For example, customer emails and reviews often contain detailed sentiments about service quality, shipment delays, and overall customer experience. By applying sentiment analysis, companies can automatically classify these texts as positive, negative, or neutral, providing immediate insights into areas that may require attention or improvement.

This method also helps in identifying recurring issues that affect customer satisfaction. For instance, frequent negative sentiments related to delayed shipments

or damaged goods can alert the company to specific operational problems that need to be addressed promptly. This proactive approach allows companies to resolve issues more efficiently, enhancing customer trust and loyalty.

The primary advantage of sentiment analysis in MTL is the ability to process and interpret large volumes of text data quickly and accurately. This automated approach reduces the need for manual review, saving time and resources. The insights gained from sentiment analysis enable more data-driven decision-making, improving overall operational efficiency and customer satisfaction.

However, there are challenges associated with sentiment analysis, including the complexity of human language, which can lead to misinterpretation of sarcasm, irony, and context. To mitigate these issues, sentiment analysis models require extensive and diverse training data to achieve high accuracy. Despite these challenges, the benefits of applying sentiment analysis in MTL are substantial, making it an essential tool for modern shipping companies seeking to enhance their operational capabilities and customer relations.

Text classification and clustering are essential NLP techniques that significantly enhance data management in MTL [9]. These techniques automatically categorize and organize large volumes of unstructured

text, such as emails, reports, and customer inquiries, improving efficiency and decision-making.

Text classification assigns predefined labels to text data based on its content. In MTL, this can be applied in several ways:

- Email management: automatically sorting emails into categories like urgent inquiries, routine updates, or marketing materials to prioritize responses and address critical issues promptly.

- Document categorization: regulatory documents, shipping manifests, and compliance reports to facilitate retrieval and processing. For example, documents can be classified into customs declarations, safety compliance, or financial records.

- Categorizing support tickets based on issues, allowing faster routing to the appropriate department, improving response times and customer satisfaction.

The typical workflow for these techniques in MTL involves several steps, as illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2. Workflow for text classification and clustering in MTL

The process starts with training data collection and preparation, followed by pre-processing and feature extraction. Classifiers are then trained and evaluated to learn the features-category mapping, which can be applied to new texts with unknown categories.

The main advantage of text classification and clustering is efficient data handling, reducing manual work and providing valuable insights for operational improvements. Challenges include language variability and integration with existing IT systems.

Deep learning models, such as BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) and GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer), can enhance NLP by offering more accurate and context-dependent text processing capabilities. In the MTL sector, these models are essential for extracting valuable information from unstructured text data (table 2).

Table 2.

Applications of deep learning models in MTL [5, 6]

Deep learning model	Application area	Description	Benefits
BERT	Email management	Automatically extracts and processes key information from customer emails and inquiries.	Reduces manual effort, ensures timely and accurate responses, enhances customer satisfaction.
	Report analysis	Analyzes and categorizes content from incident reports and operational logs.	Identifies patterns and trends, improves decision-making and operational efficiency.
	Sentiment analysis	Evaluates sentiment in customer feedback regarding shipping services.	Provides insights into customer satisfaction, helps in improving service quality and addressing issues.
GPT	Automated response generation	Generates contextually appropriate replies to customer inquiries and communications.	Enhances customer engagement, ensures consistent and informative responses, reduces response time.
	Document summarization	Summarizes lengthy regulatory documents and reports into concise formats.	Saves time, improves comprehension of critical information, supports compliance efforts.
	Predictive maintenance messaging	Analyzes maintenance logs to generate alerts and recommendations for preventive maintenance.	Reduces equipment downtime, extends lifespan of machinery, optimizes maintenance schedules.

Deep learning models such as BERT and GPT offer significant advantages for processing text messages in MTL. Their ability to understand context and semantics leads to more accurate and efficient data extraction and analysis. These models automate complex text processing tasks, reduce manual workload, and enhance operational efficiency. Despite challenges related to data quality, computational resources, and integration with existing systems, the benefits of deep learning models make them indispensable for modernizing and optimizing MTL operations. As these technologies continue to evolve, their application in MTL is expected to expand, driving further improvements in efficiency and customer satisfaction.

Case studies: use of NLP for text processing in MTL

The integration of NLP technologies in the MTL sector can lead to significant advancements in handling and analyzing large volumes of unstructured text data. Companies in this industry deal with diverse textual information, including customer inquiries, regulatory documents, incident reports, and maintenance logs.

Maersk Line, a leader in the shipping industry, is known for integrating advanced technologies, including NLP, to enhance operational efficiency. Maersk's overall commitment to digital transformation includes automating processes and improving customer interactions through technology. For example, the company has streamlined the process of amending spot bookings by allowing customers to send messages through a digital platform. Approximately 30,000 users have utilized the service from February 2023 to January 2024 [2].

Maersk's comprehensive approach to digital transformation is also reflected in its customer service operations. By integrating NLP and AI into their customer service platforms, Maersk can handle a higher volume of inquiries with greater accuracy and speed. These technologies enable the company to provide more personalized and efficient service, addressing customer needs more effectively and fostering stronger relationships. Maersk's focus on digital innovation is part of a broader trend within the maritime industry, where digitalization is seen as a key driver of competitiveness and growth. The company's efforts in this area are supported by a robust infrastructure of digital tools and platforms, which are continually updated and refined to meet evolving market demands.

Matson Inc. enhances customer service and operational efficiency through data-driven methodologies and advanced computer technologies such as Electronic Data Interchange (EDI), email, and fax. By automating the exchange of critical shipping documents, EDI reduces errors and accelerates processing times, ensuring customers receive accurate and timely information [8]. Complementary communication methods like email and fax cater to clients with varying technological capabilities, while customer support applications provide real-time updates and notifications about cargo status from receipt to delivery. This multifaceted approach ensures transparency, builds trust, and meets the diverse needs of Matson's customer base.

The process of implementing neural networks for data extraction from text messages in MTL is still in its

developmental stage. Currently, most companies rely on manual processing of the hundreds of emails that operators receive daily. Automating this process represents a contemporary and innovative direction in the industry.

Conclusion

The integration of neural networks for data extraction from text messages in MTL is a promising development that addresses the increasing complexity and volume of unstructured text data in the industry. By automating processes that were traditionally manual, such as the processing of customer inquiries, regulatory documents, incident reports, and maintenance logs, companies can achieve significant operational efficiencies and improve customer satisfaction. The application of NLP technologies, including advanced deep learning models like BERT and GPT, offers enhanced accuracy and context-aware analysis, leading to better decision-making and streamlined operations. As the technology continues to evolve, its adoption is expected to grow, further driving advancements in the MTL sector and setting new standards for efficiency and innovation.

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